

First evidences of energy performance certificate operational rating: The case of Cyprus

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Abstract. This study aims to introduce the first pieces of evidence of an operational rating scheme for energy performance certificates for the case of Cyprus, an EU member state which conducts buildings classification with asset rating. For the purpose of this study, a case building was monitored for over 12 months in Cyprus, recording over 60 sensors within the building related to heating, cooling, lighting, and appliances. A set of operational indicators were extracted and demonstrated with the purpose of establishing a dataset of operational measurements for buildings in Cyprus. Normalization practices related to occupancy and weather correction factors are also discussed. Following the guidelines of ISO 52003 on the operational rating of buildings, the study concludes with the definition of representative values for the actual energy performance of buildings in Cyprus, delivering typical operational rates for the Cypriot building stock. The case study building is also examined, with regard to its operational rating, based on the average value of the Cypriot building stock. This study aspires to set the grounds for the development of an operational rating scheme for the island state of Cyprus based on best practices and the normative framework for energy-efficient buildings.

1. Introduction

The core process for the Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) calculation lies in calculating buildings' heating and cooling loads with the use of Building Energy Performance Simulation (BEPS) tools. BEPS tools conduct energy performance calculations either based on buildings design values (known as asset rating) or based on the actual energy consumption of the buildings (known as the operational rating) [1]. While the methodology based on asset rating considers the primary energy needs without taking into account all the losses derived from the production of energy, the operational rating is based on the energy delivered to the buildings and therefore includes users' behaviors [2]. Existing buildings tend to undergo performance degradations, changes in use, and unexpected faults or malfunctions over time [3][4]. These events often result in significant deterioration of the overall system performance, inefficient operation, and unacceptable human comfort conditions. These facts underline the necessity of the employment of operational rating, as well as the deficiencies of asset rating. Among the 27 European Union (UN) Member States (MS), 11 have adopted the methodology exclusively based on asset rating. In some MSs, both the actual and calculated energy consumptions are foreseen.

1.1. Enhancement of EU building stocks

Although EPCs disclose significant data concerning the energy performance of buildings, in some EU MSs, they have currently considered an additional building document that fails to deliver valuable and interpretable information, awareness, quality, and user-friendliness, resulting in a limited acceptance among users [5][6][7]. This discrepancy is attributed to the following causes [8]:

1. Regarding the modelling software and design assumptions:
 - Inaccuracies [9] and uncertainties in the implementation of the modelling inputs [10].
 - Simplifications and inadequacies of the simulation tool [11] can lead to unrealistic inputs concerning the building design, as well as user behavior, occupancy patterns, and building management [12].
 - The quality of input data used for the simulation depends on the choices made by the model operator (e.g., design weather data, regulation type, shading factor, calculated surfaces, etc.) [13].
2. Construction quality: Deficiencies and provisioning issues during the construction process and commissioning, such as gaps in the insulation and thermal bridges, which are usually not considered in calculating energy consumption [14].
3. Discrepancies also arise during the usage stage of the building. These may include unsuitable building management and energy-unconscious users [9].

Furthermore, the revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) calls for benchmarking of buildings through Building Automation and Control System. This approach would require extensive sharing of information between buildings [15].

Based on the continuous improvement of the minimum energy requirements of EU MSs for new buildings, and in view of the nearly Zero Energy Buildings (nZEB) era, which started on the 31st of December 2020, this development will lead to the enhancement of the actual energy performance of EU MSs' building stocks. In this manner, a more active role of next-generation EPCs in policy making will be enabled.

Table 1. Energy needs [kWh/m²] for residential buildings.

Building type	Age	Space heating [kWh/m ²]	Space cooling [kWh/m ²]	Water Heating [kWh/m ²]	Lighting [kWh/m ²]	Appliances [kWh/m ²]	Cooking [kWh/m ²]
Single house	< 1981	54	72	23	8	20	6
	1981 - 2006	40	54	18	7	15	4
	> 2006	36	50	15	6	14	4
Semi-detached + Rowhouses	< 1981	59	58	23	9	21	6
	1981 - 2006	43	44	18	7	16	4
	> 2006	39	40	15	6	15	4
Apartment blocks	< 1981	45	105	23	8	19	6
	1981 - 2006	33	84	18	6	15	4
	> 2006	30	76	15	6	13	4
Other types of building	< 1981	56	53	23	4	8	0
	1981 - 2006	41	41	18	3	8	0
	> 2006	37	38	15	3	7	0

2. Energy classification

The energy classification of the case study building was conducted following the building stock as a reference method, described in the European standard 52003:2017, Energy performance of buildings

— Indicators, requirements, ratings and certificates [16] and more specifically in Article 10 – EPB rating. For this purpose, the assessment of the Cypriot building stock was conducted in accordance with the minimum requirements for class A buildings [17] [18], set by the competent authority in Cyprus, as well as on a JRC Technical Reports concerning the energy consumption of the building stock in Cyprus [19].

Table 2. Energy needs [kWh/m²] for non-residential buildings.

Building type	Age	Space heating [kWh/m ²]	Space cooling [kWh/m ²]	Water Heating [kWh/m ²]	Lighting [kWh/m ²]
Hotels and other accommodation	< 2006	65	268	40	55
	> 2006	45	183	28	50
Schools	< 2006	35	55	7	35
	> 2006	24	37	5	30
Public buildings	< 2006	49	44	5	42
	> 2006	34	30	4	37
Supermarkets and malls	< 2006	33	470	1	105
	> 2006	23	321	1	95
Hospitals and clinics	< 2006	96	181	121	70
	> 2006	66	123	83	65
Restaurants and taverns	< 2006	142	285	214	85
	> 2006	97	194	146	80
Private offices	< 2006	87	203	5	45
	> 2006	59	138	4	40
Retail shops	< 2006	41	194	5	105
	> 2006	28	132	4	95
Other	< 2006	197	358	137	70
	> 2006	134	244	93	65

The energy performance of the Cypriot building stock is presented in **Table 1 - Table 6.**

Table 3. Final energy consumption [kWh/m²] for residential buildings.

Building type	Age	Space heating [kWh/m ²]	Space cooling [kWh/m ²]	Water Heating [kWh/m ²]	Final energy consumption [kWh/m ²]
Single house	< 1981	54	72	23	149
	1981 - 2006	40	54	18	112
	> 2006	36	50	15	101
Semi-detached + Rowhouses	< 1981	59	58	23	140
	1981 - 2006	43	44	18	105
	> 2006	39	40	15	94
Apartment blocks	< 1981	45	105	23	173
	1981 - 2006	33	84	18	135
	> 2006	30	76	15	121
Other types of building	< 1981	56	53	23	132
	1981 - 2006	41	41	18	100
	> 2006	37	38	15	90

Additionally, the disparity between rural and urban areas has been factored into the equation for the residential sector.

Based on this data, the energy rating class of the Cypriot residential building stock is derived as follows:

Table 4. Energy rating class for residential building typologies (delivered energy)

Building type	Age	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Single house	< 1981	37	74	112	149	186	224	261
	1981 - 2006	37	62	87	112	137	162	187
	> 2006	37	58	80	101	122	144	165
Semi-detached + Rowhouses	< 1981	37	71	106	140	174	209	243
	1981 - 2006	37	60	82	105	128	150	173
	> 2006	37	56	75	94	113	132	151
Apartment blocks	< 1981	37	82	128	173	218	264	309
	1981 - 2006	37	70	102	135	168	200	233
	> 2006	37	65	93	121	149	177	205
Other types of building	< 1981	37	69	100	132	164	195	227
	1981 - 2006	37	58	79	100	121	142	163
	> 2006	37	55	72	90	108	125	143

Table 5. Final energy consumption [kWh/m²] for non-residential buildings.

Building type	Age	Space heating [kWh/m²]	Space cooling [kWh/m²]	Water Heating [kWh/m²]	Final energy consumption [kWh/m²]
Hotels and other accommodation	< 2006	65	268	40	373
	> 2006	45	183	28	256
Schools	< 2006	35	55	7	97
	> 2006	24	37	5	66
Public buildings	< 2006	49	44	5	98
	> 2006	34	30	4	68
Supermarkets and malls	< 2006	33	470	1	504
	> 2006	23	321	1	345
Hospitals and clinics	< 2006	96	181	121	398
	> 2006	66	123	83	272
Restaurants and taverns	< 2006	142	285	214	641
	> 2006	97	194	146	437
Private offices	< 2006	87	203	5	295
	> 2006	59	138	4	201
Retail shops	< 2006	41	194	5	240
	> 2006	28	132	4	164
Other	< 2006	197	358	137	692
	> 2006	134	244	93	471

Based on this data, the energy rating class of the Cypriot non-residential building stock is as follows:

Table 6. Energy rating class for non-residential buildings (delivered energy).

Building type	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Hotels and other accommodation	46	155	264	373	482	591	700
	46	116	186	256	326	396	466
Schools	46	63	80	97	114	131	148
	46	53	59	66	73	79	86
Public buildings	46	63	81	98	115	133	150
	46	53	61	68	75	83	90
Supermarkets and malls	46	199	351	504	657	809	962
	46	146	245	345	445	544	644
Hospitals and clinics	46	163	281	398	515	633	750
	46	121	197	272	347	423	498
Restaurants and taverns	46	244	443	641	839	1038	1236
	46	176	307	437	567	698	828
Private offices	46	129	212	295	378	461	544
	46	98	149	201	253	304	356
Retail shops	46	111	175	240	305	369	434
	46	85	125	164	203	243	282
Other	46	261	477	692	907	1123	1338
	46	188	329	471	613	754	896

3. Analytical measurements of the building

3.1. Brief description of the building's information

In this section, the related to the aforementioned indicators' tables and indicatively graphical representations of the building's measurements are shown.

The installed equipment in the building includes:

- Indoor conditions measurement devices (Temperature, Relative Humidity, CO₂) (HOBO MX1102A)
- 4 power meter data loggers (1xEG4130 Pro - 30 Input, 3xEG4115 – 15 Input).

In **Table 7**, the occupancy, surface area, and volume per floor, as well as in total based on the actual measurements of the case building in Cyprus, are presented.

Table 7. Occupancy, surface area, and volume per floor.

Floor	Number of people	Surface area (m²)	Volume (m³)
Ground floor	35	467	1450
First floor	50	487	1450
Second floor	25	487	1450
Total	110	1441	4350

Figure 1. Ground floor HVAQ.

The deployment of the heating and cooling equipment is presented in **Figure 1**, **Figure 2**, and **Figure 3**.

Figure 2. First floor HVAQ.

Figure 3. Second floor HVAQ.

3.2. Indicators' documentation

Based on the real-time measurements of the case building, the related heating and cooling, lighting, and electrical appliances indicators are documented in **Table 8**. The time step of the KPIs calculation is annual (June 21-May 22). These indicators have been calculated in relation to the occupancy, the surface area, and the volume per floor of the building.

Table 8. Annual Indicators – June 2021-May 2022.

Load	Annual Amount	Unit
Total Heating and Cooling	25.22	(kWh/m ²)
	330.33	(kWh/Occupants)
	8.34	(kWh/m ³)
Total Heating	7.31	(kWh/m ²)
	95.76	(kWh/Occupants)
	2.41	(kWh/m ³)
Total Cooling	17.91	(kWh/m ²)
	234.57	(kWh/Occupants)
	5.93	(kWh/m ³)
Total Lighting for 1 st and 2 nd floors	14.22	(kWh/m ²)
	184.57	(kWh/Occupants)
	4.76	(kWh/m ³)

	19.18	(kWh/m ²)
Total Electrical Appliances	249.10	(kWh/Occupants)
	6.43	(kWh/m ³)
Total Ground floor (October '21 – May '22)	69.60	(kWh/m ²)
	928.76	(kWh/Occupants)
	22.42	(kWh/m ³)
Total Power of the building	128.22	(kWh/m ²)
	1692.76	(kWh/Occupants)
	41.95	(kWh/m ³)

3.3. Indicative indicators' graphical representations

According to the real-time data that was measured in the case building, the graphical representations of indicators included:

- heating and cooling consumption
- heating and cooling degree days
- lighting consumption
- appliances consumption
- indoor conditions (temperature, RH, CO₂)
- total power consumption.

In **Figure 4** to **Figure 6**, the representation of heating and cooling indicators is presented.

Figure 4. Ground Floor, Heating, and Cooling energy [kWh/Day/DegreeDay].

Figure 5. First Floor, Heating and Cooling energy [kWh/Day/DegreeDay].

Figure 6. Second Floor, Heating and Cooling energy [kWh/Day/DegreeDay].

The total lighting consumption of the whole case study building per floor is depicted in the graphical representation of **Figure 7**. The total appliance consumption of the whole case building per floor is depicted in the graphical representation of **Figure 8**.

Figure 7. Total lighting consumption per floor [kWh].

Figure 8. Total appliance consumption per floor [kWh].

The total power consumption of the building per floor is depicted in the graphical representations of **Figure 9** and **Figure 10**.

Figure 9. Total power consumption of the building [kWh].

Figure 10. Total power consumption of the building per floor [kWh].

4. Conclusions

The optimum conditions for testing out technological advancements that are developed within the framework of sustainable buildings and urban environments are generated by a building setup of energy-efficient practical structures and extended smart sensor linkages. It is possible to obtain an understanding of installed equipment's operational characteristics by utilizing the volume of data and measurements it provides. This study aims to use the real-time collected annual measurements of the examined non-residential building case (offices) covered in terms of energy monitoring so as to provide data flow that fully depicts the building's status in relation to the occupancy, the surface area, and the volume per floor of the building. All essential metering equipment for operational-based EPC/dynamic KPIs analysis has been deployed, along with any parameters required for asset-based EPC/static KPIs assessment that is or cannot be included in the BIM model.

According to the European standard 52003:2017, the authors of this paper proceeded to determine the energy consumption of the building. Moreover, the main actual characteristics of the Cypriot building stock and the energy classification of the building energy efficiency certificate were examined and developed, respectively. Based on **Table 6** and the fact that the total annual energy consumption of the studied case building was measured to be 128 kWh/m², its performance for the year 2021-2022 was rated at class B, considering the building as an office building type. Consequently, through the procedure followed in this study, the energy class of residential and non-residential buildings in Cyprus can be determined.

5. References

- [1] Fokaides PA, Maxoulis CN, Panayiotou GP, Neophytou MK, Kalogirou SA. Comparison between measured and calculated energy performance for dwellings in a summer dominant environment. *Energy and Buildings*. 2011 Nov 1; 43(11):3099-105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2011.08.005>.
- [2] Energy Performance Certificates Across the EU- A mapping of national approaches, 2015; BPIE
- [3] Heo Y, Choudhary R, Augenbroe GA. Calibration of building energy models for retrofit analysis under uncertainty. *Energy and Buildings*. 2012 Apr 1; 47:550-60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2011.12.029>.
- [4] Ma Z, Wang S. Online fault detection and robust control of condenser cooling water systems in building central chiller plants. *Energy and buildings*. 2011 Jan 1; 43(1):153-65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2010.09.003>.
- [5] Sesana MM, Salvalai G. A review on Building Renovation Passport: Potentialities and barriers on current initiatives. *Energy and Buildings*. 2018 Aug 15; 173:195-205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENBUILD.2018.05.027>.
- [6] Farahani A, Wallbaum H, Dalenbäck JO. The importance of life-cycle based planning in maintenance and energy renovation of multifamily buildings. *Sustainable Cities and Society*. 2019 Jan 1; 44:715-25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.SCS.2018.10.033>.
- [7] Amecke H. The impact of energy performance certificates: A survey of German home owners. *Energy Policy*. 2012 Jul 1; 46:4-14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2012.01.064>.
- [8] Burman E, Mumovic D, Kimpian J. Towards measurement and verification of energy performance under the framework of the European directive for energy performance of buildings. *Energy*. 2014 Dec 1; 77:153-63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2014.05.102>.
- [9] Menezes AC, Cripps A, Bouchlaghem D, Buswell R. Predicted vs. actual energy performance of non-domestic buildings: Using post-occupancy evaluation data to reduce the performance gap. *Applied energy*. 2012 Sep 1; 97:355-64. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2011.11.075>.
- [10] Ahmad M, Culp CH. Uncalibrated building energy simulation modeling results. *Hvac&R research*. 2006 Oct 1; 12(4):1141-55. DOI:[10.1080/10789669.2006.10391455](https://doi.org/10.1080/10789669.2006.10391455)

- [11] Lomas KJ. The UK applicability study: an evaluation of thermal simulation programs for passive solar house design. *Building and Environment*. 1996 May 1; 31(3):197-206. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0360-1323\(95\)00050-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0360-1323(95)00050-X).
- [12] Raslan R, Davies M. Results variability in accredited building energy performance compliance demonstration software in the UK: an inter-model comparative study. *Journal of Building Performance Simulation*. 2010 Mar 1; 3(1):63-85. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19401490903477386>.
- [13] Khoury J, Alameddine Z, Hollmuller P. Understanding and bridging the energy performance gap in building retrofit. *Energy Procedia*. 2017 Sep 1; 122:217-22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2017.07.348>.
- [14] Bordass B. Energy performance of non-domestic buildings: closing the credibility gap. In: *Proceedings of the 2004 Improving Energy Efficiency of Commercial Buildings Conference 2004* Apr 21.
- [15] Dasgupta A, Prodromou A, Mumovic D. Operational versus designed performance of low carbon schools in England: Bridging a credibility gap. *HVAC&R Research*. 2012 Feb 1; 18(1-2):37-50.
- [16] ISO 52003-1:2017 Energy performance of buildings — Indicators, requirements, ratings and certificates — Part 1: General aspects and application to the overall energy performance
- [17] National Legislation, The Regulation of the Energy Efficiency of Buildings 121/2020
- [18] National Legislation, The Regulation of the Energy Efficiency of Buildings 122/2020,
- [19] Zangheri P. Building stock in Cyprus and trends to 2030'. European Commission, Joint Research Centre Technical Report. 2016.

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